

RANGE OF METAMORPHOSIS WORKS CREATED IN WORLD LITERATURE.

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Annotation: In the article, the formation of metamorphoses separated from the shell of mythology and formed independently as an artistic tool - a motif of evolution is studied on the example of the works of mature writers. In world masterpieces, it is observed that metamorphoses move from primitive thinking to artistic thinking as a motive, meet updates from the point of view of theme and idea, especially come closer to social life and acquire symbolic and metaphorical significance, adapting to modern literature. In addition, the importance of the evolution motive in expressing the socio-philosophical concept of the creator is discussed.

Keywords: Myth, mythology, metamorphosis, evolution motif, mythological thinking, primitive thinking, ancient literature, etc.

Аннотация: В статье на примере произведений зрелых писателей рассматривается формирование метаморфоз, отделившихся от оболочки мифологии и сформировавшихся самостоятельно как художественный инструмент - мотив эволюции. В мировых шедеврах наблюдается, что метаморфозы переходят от первобытного мышления к художественному мышлению как мотиву, встречаются обновления с точки зрения темы и идеи, особенно приближаются к общественной жизни и приобретают символическое и метафорическое значение, адаптируясь к современной литературе. Кроме того, обсуждается значение мотива эволюции в выражении социально-философской концепции творца.

Ключевые слова: Миф, мифология, метаморфоза, мотив эволюции, мифологическое мышление, первобытное мышление, античная литература и др.

The myths collected and compiled by the great writers of ancient literature allow us to obtain the necessary information about the genesis of the first metamorphoses. These mythological plots played a significant role in the formation of written literature of antiquity. In the first Latin novel – Apuleius’s “Metamorphoses, or the Golden Ass”, [1] the transformation of the main

character Lucius into a donkey was the first appearance of metamorphosis as a motif in written literature.

After that, world literature developed rapidly with works with traditional metamorphosis motifs one after another. In particular, the world-famous tragedy “Faust” by Johann Wolfgang Goethe (1749-1832), the founder of modern German literature, also contains countless metamorphoses. In this work, where traditional plots and images from folk folklore are reworked and enriched with the author’s concept, the motif of evolution creates unparalleled opportunities for the writer, especially in terms of artistic time - breaking the boundaries of time and space. As events unfold, this motif is realized by the devil (Mephistopheles) and images of gods and goddesses, goddesses, fairies, who are outside the material world.

Throughout the work, you can see countless metamorphoses in Mephistopheles’s repeated transformation into a dog, when he wraps Faust in his cloak, when the wise Faust immediately turns back into a young man, when champagne and wine turn into fire through a hole drilled in the “Auerbach Cellar in Leipzig”, [2]when the wine in the cup that Faust is handed turns into fire in the witch’s house, as well as when Mephistopheles takes the form of an old man in the chapter “On Walpurgis Night” of the Tragedy, and in other episodic images and details. Gogol’s story “The Nose” differs from the metamorphoses of antiquity in that it reveals its essence and wide possibilities. According to the brief plot of the work, the hero of the work, Major Kovalyov, loses his nose.[3] He sees his nose in the uniform of a high-ranking official. His nose has already taken on the form of a person and does not want to return to his face. Later, he learns that his nose has surpassed him, having reached the rank of State Counselor. This story tells of an official whose pride does not allow him to look down on ordinary people of lower status.

In Kafka’s story “Metamorphosis”, the main plot line, in which events develop along the motif of metamorphosis, is also reflected. Gregor Samsa, a responsible, hardworking, family breadwinner, wakes up in the morning to find himself transformed into some kind of creature. But this state does not worry him at all, on the contrary, he is embarrassed by the inconveniences that have arisen as a result. He feels sorry for his family members more than for himself, and lives in fear of their economic situation. Gradually, Gregor becomes a nuisance to them. And his father, hanging on the wall, hits his son with an apple, crippling him, and only after the death of this creature does his family members feel relieved.

Perhaps, if Grigor Zamza had not been transformed into a creature, he would not have experienced this tragic fate, but with his transformation, he witnessed his place in society and the true attitude of his family members towards him. Kafka once again renews the essence of the transformation motif with this story.

In Mikhail Bulgakov's works written in the direction of magical realism, "The Master and Margarita" and "The Heartless", we also encounter the transformation of one species into another. In particular, in the story "The Heartless", one winter day, Filip Filipovich brings a dog named Sharik, who is hungry and cold, to his house and performs an operation on Sharik, that is, he tests his research on rejuvenating a person by transplanting a human pituitary gland into a dog. The dog gradually begins to turn into a person.[4]

Shvonder convinces the dog, who has fallen under his influence, that he is a proletarian suffering from bourgeois oppression, in the example of Philip Philipovich and Ivan Arnoldovich. Shvonder, who is the chairman of the household committee, gives Sharik a job and demands that Philip give him a name, and achieves his goal. Sharikov even shoots them with a pistol once. After that, the professor performs another operation on him and turns him back into a dog. The author uses the motif of transformation to reveal some of the vices inherent in humans through the image of a dog.

In the novel "The Master and Margarita", we see that Margarita, who turns into a 20-year-old beautiful girl after applying the magic oil given to her by Azazello to her whole body, Nikolai Ivanovich, who turns into a pig as a result of the oil applied to his head, and Woland, who is the personification of Satan, and the characters around him, transform into various forms through magic.[5] "Natasha's excitement took over, and she inadvertently rubbed it against Nikolai Ivanovich, and he froze in surprise. The face of this venerable man living on the ground floor twisted and turned into a pig's snout, and hooves grew from his arms and legs."

We meet another motif of transformation in P. Coelho's "The Alchemist." The main character of the work, Santiago, who sets out on a journey to his goal, comes to understand the secret of the entire universe in the course of events. At the same time that the old alchemist's years of experience have turned stone into gold, Santiago, without realizing it himself, also understands the secret of the entire universe and speaks the only language of the universe, when he falls into the hands of horsemen in the desert. The alchemist asks for three days to

save his life, saying that Santiago can turn into the wind. At first, Santiago, who did not believe that he could do it, turns into the wind on the third day.[6]

The masterpieces of world literature, the examples of which are given above, were created by different writers in different times and places, and metamorphoses in all of them play a special role in describing the idea of the work and the artistic, philosophical, social concept of the author. It should be noted that in the works of world literature of recent centuries, metamorphoses have acquired a new meaning and essence, somewhat moving away from their mythological roots.

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